

Literature Review Revision Checklist

Introduction

- Does the introduction clearly state the purpose and scope of the literature review?
- Is there a logical progression from the general context to the specific focus of the review?
- Have you identified the significance of the topic and its relevance to the field of study?
- Are key terms and concepts defined to provide clarity for the reader?
- Does the introduction end with a clear thesis statement or research question?

Structure and Organization

- Is the literature review organized logically, with themes, concepts, or chronology?
- Are paragraphs and sections well-developed and clearly related to the overall topic?
- Have you included headings and subheadings to guide the reader through different sections?
- Do transitions between paragraphs and sections flow smoothly and logically?

Coverage of Literature

- Have you included a sufficient number of relevant sources to provide a comprehensive overview?
- Is the literature review recent and up-to-date? Are there any gaps in recent research?
- Have you critically evaluated the quality and relevance of each source?
- Have you identified conflicting viewpoints or areas of debate within the literature?
- Have you integrated sources to build a coherent narrative rather than listing summaries?

Critical Analysis

- Have you synthesized and analyzed the literature rather than just summarizing each source?
- Have you identified patterns, themes, or trends across different sources? (relational research)
- Have you evaluated the methodologies used in the studies reviewed?
- Have you discussed strengths and weaknesses of different studies or methodologies?
- Have you identified areas where further research is needed?

Writing Style and Language

- Is the writing formal and objective, avoiding colloquial language or personal opinions?
- Are sentences clear, concise, and grammatically correct?
- Have you avoided excessive jargon, ensuring accessibility for readers outside your field?
- Have you used appropriate transitions and linking words to enhance coherence?
- Have you consistently followed the citation style required by your institution or field?

Conclusion

- Does the conclusion summarize the main findings and insights from the literature review?
- Have you emphasized the implications of the reviewed literature for your research?
- Have you suggested possible avenues for future research based on gaps identified?

- Does the conclusion reinforce the significance of the topic within the broader field of study?

Formatting and Presentation

- Have you formatted the literature review according to the guidelines provided (e.g. margins)?
- Is the bibliography or reference list accurate and complete?
- Have you double-checked all citations and references for accuracy?
- Are all figures, tables, and appendices clearly labeled and referenced in the text?
- Have you proofread the entire literature review for spelling, punctuation, and typographical errors?

Checklist Response

Study: "Examining Factors Affecting Depression and Anxiety Among Medical Students in Post-Soviet Countries: A Systematic Literature Review"

Introduction:

- Yes, the introduction outlines the purpose and scope of the literature review, offering the reader a clear and comprehensive understanding of its aim and underlying rationale.
- The review follows a logical structure, transitioning from the broader context to the specific focus.
- Yes, the significance of the topic is effectively established, with a clear explanation of its relevance and contribution to the field, demonstrating why the review is both timely and necessary.
- All key terms and concepts are clearly defined. We have defined such terms as depression and anxiety.
- Yes, the introduction concludes with a well-articulated thesis statement that sets the direction for the literature review.

Structure and Organization:

- Yes, the literature review is organized in a coherent manner, structured around key themes and concepts that provide a clear framework for understanding the development of ideas.
- Each paragraph and section are well-developed, with content that directly supports and relates to the overall focus of the review.
- Yes, appropriate headings and subheadings are used.
- Yes, the transitions are clearly considered, helping the review flow smoothly from one paragraph and section to the next.

Coverage of Literature:

- We did our best to search multiple databases, but some countries were not well represented in our results. This was not intentional – it is simply that research on medical students' mental health is limited in those areas, often due to stigma and underreporting.
- The search was performed from September to November 2024.
- Yes, the review critically evaluates the quality and relevance of each source, highlights conflicting viewpoints and debates within the literature, and integrates findings to form a cohesive narrative rather than presenting summaries.

Critical Analysis: Yes, the review goes beyond summarizing by synthesizing and analyzing the literature, identifying key themes across sources, discussing the limitations of cross-sectional studies, and highlighting gaps where further research is needed.

Writing Style and Language: We followed a formal writing style, ensuring that all statements in the manuscript are supported by existing literature. The manuscript was thoroughly reviewed for errors and English language issues by all co-authors. Additionally, it was checked using Trinka AI Grammar Checker (Paid version), a web-tool designed for checking academic and technical writing. We avoided the use of jargon, used appropriate transitions and linking words to improve coherence in our manuscript, and followed the citation style mentioned by a scientific journal.

Conclusion: Yes, the conclusion summarizes the main findings and highlights their implications for health professions in medical education, while possible avenues for future research are outlined in the Discussion section.

Formatting and Presentation

Yes, the literature review is properly formatted according to the guidelines, all references and citations are accurate and complete, figures and tables are clearly labeled and referenced, and the entire text has been thoroughly proofread for errors.